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Localization of sustainable development goals (SDGs) in Bangladesh: a case study on the ministry of environment, forest and climate change

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Bangladesh is a top-performing country in achieving Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Bangladesh has taken various initiatives in localizing SDGs at various levels from grassroots to central and has aligned SDGs with national development plans like the 7th Five Year Plan. The localization of SDGs depends on strategic issues, planning, policy, medium and long term vision, appropriate initiatives, addressing complex cross-cutting issues, investments, know-how, technical-intellectual capacity, and operational management. For localizing and implementing SDGs a public organization should be competitive in the management taking care of the integration with other organs and should adopt the initiatives in which the business is inserted for the meeting targets and indicators of SDGs. To check the progress of localization and implementation of the related targets and indicators of SDGs the organizational analysis is essential. The study aimed at examining the linkages among the allocation of business, the targets of SDGs and the initiatives taken by the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change. Secondary data was used for this analysis. According to the mandates, this ministry is broadly resonated with 26 targets of SDGs. The ministry has taken various initiatives to reach most of the concerned targets and has a wider scope to take more programmes or projects to achieve some targets for 2020 described in SDG 14 and 15. There are few dots in the allocation of business which should be redefined incorporating international frameworks and bindings.

Keywords: SDGs, linkages, business allocation, targets, dots